

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF EMBEDDED SOLAR POWERED WATER PUMP WITH WATER LEVEL AND SOIL MOISTURE SENSOR

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on designing and fabricating an embedded solar water pump that has embedded water level and soil moisture sensors to design an efficient irrigation system with less usage of water and cheaper rearing without the compromise of crop health. Renewable energy in the form of power from the sun through photovoltaic panels is deployed in the system for powering the pump and sensors, and all this is powered by energy stored in a 12V battery. Significant components include the ultrasonic water level sensor for managing pump function and multiple soil moisture sensors that control irrigation based on real-time soil hydration data. The Arduino microcontroller serves as the system's central processing unit, where inputs from the sensors are then managed to regulate water flow appropriately. Research follows a design and development methodology, which includes phases for analysis, design, construction, and evaluation. A wide range of simulated environmental conditions will be exposed to the test system to check its performance towards the possible revolution in the management of agricultural water. The proposed solution represents an automated eco-friendly approach to irrigation support for sustainable agricultural practice and multiple applications in farming.

Keywords: *Design and Fabrication, water irrigation, water level and soil moisture sensor, water pumping system, Photovoltaic (PV) panels*

INTRODUCTION

The biggest global challenge in terms of agriculture sustainability lies in those regions where water is in short supply and the cost of energy is high and tends to inhibit the productivity of farming. Contrary to the use of the electrical grid or the fossil fuel-powered pump irrigation system that sows environmental degradation through operational pollution and increased operational costs, there is now a ready solution like solar-powered irrigation. It essentially acts as an eco-friendly and low-cost means for the running of water pumps by tapping renewable energy. The reliance on non-renewable sources of energy significantly decreases, while encouraging sustainable practices within farming.

Photovoltaic (PV) panels were often used for agricultural operations, especially in remote areas or where the use of an alternative energy source is desired. In particular, they have been demonstrated time and time again to reliably produce sufficient electricity directly from solar radiation (sunlight) to power livestock and irrigation watering systems (Naik et al., 2023; Ikechiamaka et al., 2024; Agoylo et al., 2024). Ayundyahrini (2023) claimed that water pumping is one of the simplest and most appropriate uses for photovoltaic ranging from crop irrigation to stock watering to domestic uses. Ikechiamaka (2024) also added that the system has been recognized as suitable solution for grid-isolated rural locations in poor countries where there are high levels of solar radiation.

Smart irrigation systems ensure proper management of water by enhancing this aspect of their management through real-time monitoring and control of the use of water (Edodi et al., 2022). In other words, an automated irrigation system should include embedded sensors like soil moisture sensors and water level sensors. These sensors can effectively regulate the amount of water that needs to be available to the plant at the right time and minimize losses due to over- or under-irrigation and preserve water and reduce crop stress.

The focus of this research is on the design and fabrication of an embedded solar-powered water pump with water level and soil moisture sensors. The proposed system will, therefore, be a sustainable irrigation solution that is capable of automatically adjusting to environmental conditions based on sensor data for control of the pump. The water level sensor will ensure that the pump will function only when a sufficient water supply is available. The soil moisture sensor would monitor the hydration status of the soil to irrigation in case. Through this automated, yet energy efficient system, it aims at improving crop yields and reducing the consumption of water and farming cost consumptions. It intends to contribute to sustainable agriculture by developing an intelligent, solar-powered irrigation system well adapted for different farming applications, easy to adopt by farmers and obliterating the problems associated with traditional irrigation. The system will be evaluated for performance under different environmental

conditions to assess its potential for revolutionizing water management practices in agriculture.

Research Objectives

Generally, this study aimed to design and fabricate an embedded solar powered water pump with soil moisture and water level sensor. Specifically, it aims:

1. To determine the materials and equipment needed for the embedded solar powered water pump; and
 2. To design a wooden solar panel rack.
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METHOD AND MATERIALS

Method

This study was conducted as design and development based on reviewing data collected from previously developed solar powered water pumping system. It underwent four stages of development: analysis, design, construction and evaluation. The analysis stage was concerned with analyzing and comparing the prevailing design of solar powered water pumping system and its components. Designing stage deals with the coming up of a design of an embedded solar powered water pumping system showing a unique characteristic not common to existing design. Construction phase on the other hand stated the procedures undertaken in fabricating an embedded solar powered water pump. Evaluation stage pertains to the actual testing of the water pumping system by the proponent and expert.

Construction of embedded solar powered water pumping system

Figure 1 presents the plan layout of the solar-powered water pumping system with a photovoltaic (PV) array situated on a wooden table of sizes 21 x 44 x 29 inches. Aluminum casing is offered as a support stand, specifically for ease of assembly and disassembly using general-purpose threaded coach screws with bright zinc plating that will securely lock but flex when possible, during any adjustments to the installation.

The unit features a 12V battery together with a portable box casing for the solar charge controller to really streamline transportation as well as protect the components from environmental impacts. The solar panel charges this battery to maintain reliable water pump and sensor power sources.

In this particular case, a minimum of 200-liter capacity recycled plastic drum is working as a storage tank for water. There's an ultrasonic sensor mounted top down on the water tank that has to measure water level; hence switches on and off the pump based on the given parameters. The critical low watermark in case of this device is 850 millimeters, where the given pump will be switched on, while an upper threshold level of

100 millimeters works as the critical high watermark above which the pump gets switched off.

There are three moisture sensors that have been attached to the rice paddy for controlling the irrigation. The signals these sensors deliver are interpreted by an Arduino Uno, which then interprets the signal in order to regulate the flow of solenoid valves that handle the water flowing from the reserve tank. The soil moisture levels fall into the categories below:

- "Wet" (400-600): The valve remains closed as the soil has sufficient moisture.
- "Moderately Wet" (101-399): The valve may open if irrigation is necessary to maintain optimal moisture levels.
- "Dry" (0-100): The valve opens to allow water flow, ensuring the soil is adequately irrigated.

The system would surely prove efficient and effective in water usage because it automates the irrigating process; in that, there is no need for electricity as it is totally powered by solar energy. Hence, it will certainly serve as an eco-friendly solution for sustainable agriculture. Introducing soil moisture sensors and water level monitoring ensures that water is used efficiently, and there will be hardly any waste if the soil is not hydrated sufficiently.

Figure 1. Layout of embedded solar powered water pumping system

Figure 2 shows the diagram of a solar-powered automated water pumping system designed for irrigation. Here's an overview of the components and how they interact:

- Photovoltaic (PV) Panels: The system consists of two PV panels connected parallel or series to collect solar energy. These panels convert sunlight into electrical energy to power the system.
- Charge controller: The power from the PV panels is transferred to a charge controller. The charge controller controls the amount of voltage and current leaving the solar panel or panels, thereby safely charging the batteries without either deep discharge or overcharging the batteries, which may damage the batteries.
- Batteries: The charge in the batteries stores the electrical energy produced by the PV panels. Thus, even when there is no sunlight, as during nighttime or even cloudy days, power would be provided to the pump and other system components.
- Pump: The pump would get its power from the stored energy in the batteries to pull water up from a source such as a well or river and then dispense it into the water tank.
- Water Tank The system also has a water tank to store the pumped water. The water tank will be equipped with an ultrasonic ranging sensor to measure the water level. Such a sensor will give real-time data on the water content in the tank.
- Ultrasonic Ranging Sensor: This is installed atop the water tank. This measures how far away the water's surface is. This makes it easier to automate pump operations on the basis of the water level in the tank to avoid overflow or dry run.
- Water Meter: A water meter is provided along the pipeline that measures the volume of water being pumped into the tank. This can check the consumption of water and might be helpful for monitoring and maintenance of the system.
- Arduino Uno: It acts as the central processing unit of the system. It will accept inputs from the ultrasonic sensor, water meter, and soil moisture sensors and send controls to the pump and solenoid valves according to the logic it has received through the program.
- Soil Moisture Sensors are multiple installations that send back to Arduino information regarding the amounts of hydration levels of the soil. The Arduino uses this information to determine whether or not to open or close up the valves controlling the irrigation network. By regulating the water coming out from the tank into the farmland, sensors are used to maintain optimal soil moisture.

Figure 2. Diagram of the Embedded Solar Pumping System

Figure 3. Design of the wooden solar panel rack

Assembling of Embedded Solar Powered Water Pumping System

Below are the detailed steps in putting together the embedded solar-powered water pump system. The process involved establishing solar components, integration of sensors, and configuring automated controls.

Figure 4.1 Steps in assembling embedded solar powered water pump

A

4. Mount the ultrasonic ranging sensor and the Arduino at the top of the water tank. Then connect the pump in the Arduino

5. lay the 3-soil moisture sensor in the center of the rice field and connect it to the Arduino.

6. Connect the solenoid valve in the water tank to the Arduino.

B

Figure 4.2 Steps in assembling embedded solar powered water pump

B

7. Connect the water outlet of the pump and laid the water hose to the water tank. Then install in between the water meter.

8. Finally, check all connections making sure that all electrical connections and devices are waterproof to avoid electrocution and damage of the equipment.

Figure 4.3 Steps in assembling embedded solar powered water pump

Materials

The materials for constructing the casing and support for the solar panel were locally available wood and aluminum procured in the local store in Sogod, Southern Leyte to lessen transportation and any incidental expenses. Nonetheless, materials and equipment not available in the locality were canvassed and procured in either Tacloban, Cebu City or online. Though online order and purchase took two or three days only but if the ordered item was not the correct one it would take another two or three days before another would arrive. The following were the materials and equipment's needed:

Materials needed:

- Electrical wire
- Electrical tape and Teflon
- fittings
- general purpose threaded coach bright zinc-plated
- garden hose (3/4 inches diameter x 10 meters)
- nails (no.2 and 3)
- wood

Equipment needed:

- Arduino Uno
 - Plastic drum (200 liters capacity)
 - Deep cycle Battery (12 V)
 - 2 x 16 LCD Display
 - Male-Female jumper wire
 - Female-Female jumper wire
 - 2 channel relay
 - Soil moisture sensor and Solenoid valve
 - Solar charge controller
 - Solar panels (100 or 50 W)
 - Submersible water pump (DC 12 V, 120 watts)
 - Ultrasonic ranging sensor
 - water meter
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DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The developed embedded solar water pumping system successfully integrates renewable energy and smart irrigation technologies to optimize water usage in agriculture. It is equipped with solar panels, a 12V battery, a submersible pump, soil moisture sensors, an ultrasonic water level sensor, and an Arduino microcontroller that allows full automation of irrigation based on environmental conditions. All the parts that constitute the system are, in fact, identical to the ones identified in Naik et al. (2023); Keerthana (2023), are fundamentals of solar-powered water pumping solutions. Pramanik et al. (2022) also confirmed that inclusion of charge controller, water level and soil moisture sensor enhanced the overall system functionality (Pramanik et al., 2022; Gnanavel et al., 2022).

Adding sensors to the system (Zhu et al., 2022) upgraded its functionality by allowing real-time adjustments that will be made on the flow of water, thus minimizing wastages. For instance, the soil moisture sensors could only run the pump if and when there was a sign that water was needed based on the soil conditions. The ultrasonic water level sensor would also not let the pump work if the supply of water was low to prevent damaging the pump to optimize sustainability (Djalilov et al., 2023). This promotes resource-friendly consumption of water by reducing over-irrigation and crop stress occurrences.

Conclusion

The experiment demonstrates that a solar-powered water pumping system can be embedded in a farm setting to greatly enhance the use of irrigation, especially in remote or off-grid locations. The difficulty encountered by local farmers is in assembling the system because most of the assembly components cannot be sourced locally.

Recommendation

It is recommended that future research works should be channeled towards greater utilization of local materials to enhance system adoption. Moreover, further testing under diverse environmental conditions and further optimization of design could make it even more reliable and effective.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly followed ethical compliance guidelines to uphold the integrity and ethical standards of the research process. Participants were guaranteed the right to withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity were rigorously protected throughout the research, with data securely stored and accessible only to the research team. The study was conducted with a commitment to the well-being of the participants, ensuring that no harm resulted from their involvement.

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